

Milestone:

MS36 - Second Stakeholders forum - Stakeholder forum newsletter produced

Lead Participant:

ELIXIR Hub

Author:

Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub)

Due:

September 2024

Date Of Completion:

8 November 2024

Means of Verification

A special issue of the GDI newsletter with a short summary, the presentation slides of the Stakeholders Forum and the GDI D1.3 Wider communications strategy was sent to 276 subscribers on 8 November 2024. ([Link to the newsletter preview](#))

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

The newsletter was delayed as the Stakeholder Forum was held in mid-October.

Project participants & others

Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub)

Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub)

Arshiya Merchant (ELIXIR Hub)

Next action steps

- Promote the GDI newsletter on social media platforms.
- Maintain the GDI newsletter with quarterly updates and annual special issue after the GDI Stakeholder Forum.

